

For the treatment of cystic fibrosis, RNA medicines, gene transfer therapies, and gene editing treatments have potential

Motaz Dowaidar^{1,2}

¹Department of Bioengineering, King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran 31261, Saudi Arabia.

²Interdisciplinary Research Center for Hydrogen and Energy Storage (IRC-HES), King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Dhahran, 31261, Saudi Arabia

Abstract- Many unique genetic procedures have been created to reach the heart of the cystic fibrosis (CF) problem, overcoming a defective gene, and advances in the nucleic acid treatment industry have made these methods much more viable as potential remedies. However, before any of these approaches can be used in clinical settings, a number of hurdles must be overcome, including determining which organs should be targeted for the most robust effect with the least amount of potential harm; determining which cells should be targeted in each organ; and determining what constitutes a successful treatment. Another factor to consider is that, unlike many other treatments, gene therapy and gene editing will need advancing clinical trials ahead without data from healthy adult control cohorts; rather, phase 1 studies will require CF patients. Furthermore, we must select which patients should be included in the initial studies for mutation-agnostic methods: should we include all patients, even if effective modulator therapy is available? Clearly, if we are to be successful, we will have to face some significant challenges, and we will have to do it as a cohesive group, as we have always done.

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective modulator treatment has the ability to alter the health and long-term results of cystic fibrosis (CF) patients. These treatments improve the function of the patients' mutant cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR), allowing the CFTR channel to operate again. 1–6, Although the combination of high-throughput screening of small molecule libraries and medicinal chemistry has yielded some fantastic new effective modulator medicines, it is doubtful that this strategy will provide a game-changing medication for everyone. Partly because even the most promising modulator therapies have a wide range of responses and are still being studied. Furthermore, roughly 10% of CF patients do not generate a mutant protein to regulate, potentiate, or optimize, and such treatments are unlikely to be of considerable value to these individuals. Small chemical treatment to boost protein expression in individuals with nonsense mutations like PTC124 has proven to be significantly more difficult than anticipated. 7 This patient population necessitates the development of innovative treatment techniques. Genetic-based medicines, such as ribonucleic acid (RNA) therapies, deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) therapies, and gene editing technologies, will be used to develop these novel treatments. In CF-affected cells, each strategy will result in functional CFTR expression. These techniques, in theory, would need less frequent dosage than effective modulators, which are administered daily. Treatments based on RNA, for example, might be provided on a regular basis. In the end, certain gene-altering therapies might be used only once in a lifetime, resulting in a permanent cure. This review will look at the promise of RNA treatments, gene transfer therapies, and gene editing treatments for the treatment of CF, as well as the hurdles that will need to be overcome as we try to harness the power of these new medicines to achieve a one-time cure.

II. RIBONUCLEIC ACID

We must evaluate a range of RNA molecules when evaluating RNA as a medicinal agent.¹⁻¹³ RNA is a single-stranded nucleic acid that is made up of nucleotide bases joined by a ribose phosphate backbone. It is required for a variety of cell processes, including gene regulation, protein synthesis, and amino acid transfer. There are many different forms of RNA, but just a few of them are being studied for their therapeutic potential in CF. They include messenger RNA (mRNA), transfer RNA (tRNA), and oligonucleotides, which are smaller RNA molecules. Different groups of CF patients are expected to benefit from different RNA methods. Engineered transfer RNAs, for example, are expected to benefit patients with nonsense mutations. mRNA treatment, on the other hand, is anticipated to help all CF patients, regardless of mutation. Antisense oligonucleotides have the potential to treat people with a range of mutations, including those that affect splicing.

First, we'll look into the therapeutic potential of mRNA. The blueprint for creating proteins like CFTR is mRNA. mRNA is normally

transcribed from DNA in the nucleus before leaving the nucleus and going to the endoplasmic reticulum, the cell's protein-making machinery, where the ribosome will convert the mRNA into a protein. After that, the protein passes via the Golgi apparatus, where it undergoes final protein changes before reaching its final destination, which is the cell membrane in the case of CFTR.

To restore CFTR activity by mRNA delivery, mRNA must be supplied to essential cell types. For a variety of reasons, including the molecule's size, distribution will be problematic, necessitating the development of specialized delivery methods capable of protecting and facilitating its distribution. 11 and 14 Once transported, mRNA must be identified by the cell's protein assembly system in order for the blueprint, mRNA, to be correctly translated, resulting in full-length CFTR proteins that travel to the cell surface. Clearly, this is a difficult procedure with several checkpoints and choke spots to navigate.

There are now clinical trials looking at the potential of mRNA in a variety of disorders, including CF. The RESTORE-CF trial (NCT03375047) is one such study, which is looking at a lipid-based specialized nanoparticle carrier for mRNA. MRT5005 is an experimental medication that is aerosolized and breathed into the lungs. As an outcome measure, changes in lung function, i.e. changes in FEV₁, will be examined. The findings of this study might give proof of concept that mRNA might be a potential new treatment for cystic fibrosis.

Engineered transfer RNAs are another RNA method that might be used to alleviate nonsense mutations. Engineered transfer RNAs are intended to add an amino acid to an elongating peptide instead of terminating protein creation with a stop codon. 15 tRNAs are tiny RNA molecules that are essential for protein synthesis. The ribosome decodes the mRNA message, which is then translated into a growing protein. This is accomplished through the use of tRNAs, which are specialized RNAs that bond with mRNA and transport amino acids, the building blocks of proteins, to the ribosome, allowing for peptide elongation. tRNAs transport amino acids to the ribosome, where they are assembled into proteins. There is no transfer RNA with an amino acid to add to the forming protein when there is a nonsense mutation, also known as a premature stop codon, in the mRNA, and protein creation ends. Engineered tRNAs, on the other hand, recode the termination codon by adding an amino acid building block, allowing the peptide to be produced. This technique has been successful in boosting read through stop codons in CF airway epithelial cells that were treated in culture, resulting in full length CFTR protein, according to research from various scientists, including the Lueck group. 15

Antisense RNA oligonucleotide treatment is an alternative to the RNA methods outlined above. Antisense oligonucleotides (ASO) are single-stranded RNA molecules that are designed to either impede or interfere with mRNA creation, or to facilitate or increase mRNA breakdown. 12 Despite the fact that over 40 clinical trials have been conducted to investigate the therapeutic potential of antisense oligonucleotides, only four drugs have achieved FDA clearance. There are no FDA-approved medicines for CF. 8 and 12 This serves as a reminder of how tough it is to get a promising medication to the finish line of clinical trials. So, what role may ASOs play in CF? Splice site mutations are one of the mutant types that might benefit from ASOs. 8, 16, and 17 Splice site alterations, such as 3489C > G + 10KB, create a cryptic site, resulting in abnormal mRNA and nonfunctional proteins.

ASOs are being developed by research teams to block the cryptic splice site, allowing normal mRNA and full-length CFTR protein to be generated and functional. For the 3849C > G + 10KB mutation, Dr. Kerem and colleagues created customized ASOs. When these ASOs are applied to airway epithelial cells, CFTR is appropriately spliced and normal protein is generated. In addition, the function of the CFTR gene is restored.

To conclude, there are a few RNA methods with therapeutic potential in CF. Many of these RNA methods are being investigated as possible CF therapies. However, there are obstacles that must be solved before these techniques may be considered effective therapies. The obstacles include, but are not limited to, guaranteeing effective therapeutic agent distribution to all key tissues; guaranteeing RNA stability so that the therapy can last longer; and recognizing and reducing the possibility for off-target effects and reagent toxicity. 12

2.1 Gene therapy/editing of genes

Gene transfer treatment, in which a healthy copy of the gene is injected into cells, and gene editing, in which the endogenous CFTR gene is corrected instead of giving cells with an extra copy of the CFTR gene, are two further nucleic acid techniques. 8, 9 Endogenous mutations must be addressed for gene repair to occur. To make this modification, a number of gene editing methods can be used. For the CF community, gene therapy is not a novel concept. James Wilson, MD PhD, highlighted the possible use of adenoviral vectors to transport the recently found CFTR gene to the airways of CF patients at a Plenary presentation at the 1989 North American Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Conference. Following that, major research programs developed potential gene therapy vectors, and multiple clinical trials were conducted to deliver CFTR to airway cells, but none of these efforts resulted in significant consistent clinical efficacy, despite the fact that some level of correction may have occurred. ages 18 to 26 These studies and research endeavors, on the other hand, have taught us a great deal and advanced the discipline. Today, there are over 1000 Phase 1 trials, over 500 Phase 2 studies, and around 100 Phase 3 studies in the works for gene therapy, which falls within the regenerative medicine umbrella. The FDA has authorized gene therapy medicines for a variety of disorders, including malignancies, thalassemia, hereditary blindness, 32, 33, and spinal muscular atrophy type 1 (SMA1) (SMA). 34 SMA is a severe condition in which most infants die by their second birthday from complications of their neurodegenerative condition, but because of efficient gene therapy, patients are

now able to live without the use of a ventilator for far longer than they could have expected. 36-34 Researchers have been able to optimize the delivery of the gene therapy vector in all of these circumstances where gene therapy has advanced to the therapeutic realm. In the majority of these cases, the gene therapy vector only had to be given to a single cell type or a small body location, which is in stark contrast to the demands of a CF patient.

The United Kingdom (UK) consortium completed the most recent big gene therapy clinical study for CF in 2014.13, 37, and 39 This study used a nonviral vector that was regularly delivered to the airway over the course of a year. The therapy was shown to be highly safe and well tolerated, but its effectiveness was low, which was most likely due to inadequate transport of the gene therapy particles to the required cells. So, similar to RNA treatments, conveyance is our largest difficulty and has been the main focus of research efforts for gene transfer treatments. It is critical to develop high-efficiency vectors that can enhance the delivery of the CFTR gene to the required cells. Vectors or delivery systems can be created from lipids and polymers or can be created from viruses such as adeno associated virus (AAV) or lentiviruses. When it comes to viral vectors, researchers aren't depending on nature to create the perfect virus; instead, they're aiming to create the finest virus capsid they can. Designer vectors created by Steines and colleagues at the University of Iowa have a considerably stronger affinity for the airway cells that need to be corrected in CF. 40 They created a library of all the proteins in the viral capsid and used it to discover the viral capsid that delivered cargo to airway cells the best by combining them in different ways and then giving them to a pig. The same method may be used to find the most effective delivery mechanism for any tissue. Dahlmans et al.41, 42 reported on a similar technique using lipid and polymer-based vectors. They've devised a method for finding the optimal particles for systemic distribution, allowing them to target all of the tissues affected by CF. Several large CF gene therapy initiatives are employing these cutting-edge technologies to discover and create appropriate vectors for high-efficiency delivery, allowing gene therapy for cystic fibrosis to progress.

Following that, we'll go over the many gene editing technologies that may be used to edit or change a patient's gene to fix a sequence mutation. Several clinical trials are under underway to test the efficacy of these medicines in the treatment of cancer, sickle cell disease, and retinal illnesses. CFTR mutations have been corrected using a variety of gene editing techniques, including clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR/Cas) ,43 zinc finger nucleases (ZFN) ,44-48 transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs) Peptide nucleic acid (PNA)/DNA peptide nucleic acid (PNA)/DNA peptide nucleic acid (PNA)/DNA peptide nucleic acid (50 and 51 In the case of CF, all gene editing research is in the preclinical stage. 52 With the CFTR gene, CF patients will face particular problems that will lead to illness. To correct the gene's defect, each mutation will require its own set of editing tools.

Airway epithelial cells have been corrected using zinc finger nucleases. In induced pluripotent stem cells, Crane and colleagues discovered that ZFN could correct CFTR and restore CFTR function. 48 In CF patients' intestinal organoids, CRISPR/Cas9 was employed to repair CFTR and restore function. 43 cells were collected from patients by rectal biopsy, and the cells were then cultivated and enlarged in culture to make miniature replicas of the gut called organoids. The researchers used CRISPR/Cas9 editing techniques to fix the CFTR mutation in the organoids, then used a swelling test to assess CFTR activity in the treated and untreated organoids.

They observed considerable CFTR function in the treated organoids, showing that CFTR could be corrected. The formation of tiny peptide nucleic acids, which are nucleic acids that are similar to DNA but contain a peptide backbone instead of a sugar backbone, is used in the triplex producing PNA/DNA technique.

PNAs 51, 53, and 54 can be engineered to attach to DNA near a mutation that has to be corrected. When this PNA is supplied to a cell with donor DNA, the cell's endogenous repair systems are notified that the PNA has attached to the DNA and distorted the helix, causing endogenous repair mechanisms to activate, allowing for recombination and mutation correction. PNA/DNA given to CF airway epithelial cells through nanoparticles can restore CFTR activity in CF cells with the W1282X mutation, G542X mutation, or F508del mutation. 51, 53, and 54. In mice models of CF, PNA/DNA nanoparticles may be given in vivo by inhalation or systemically. 53 We may notice alterations in the respiratory tract when the particles are administered topically. We can notice alterations in the respiratory and gastrointestinal systems when they are administered systemically.

III. THERAPIES BASED ON CELLS

Ex-vivo gene therapy corrects a gene flaw before returning repaired cells to the patient. CAR T therapy^{27, 28} and epidermolysis bullosa, a rare skin condition, have both been highly successful with this technique. 57-55 Will this, however, work in CF? CF-affected cells would need to be fixed in the laboratory utilizing one of the latest gene editing or gene transfer technologies to be a feasible alternative for the CF population. Following that, the repaired cells would be sent to the desired organ, where they would be required to operate properly. 60-58

The proof of principle comes from Stanford University researchers who used Cas9 delivered through AAV vectors to fix the gene abnormality in primary CF airway basal cells. Purified corrected basal cells were then placed in a rat's sinus cavity to determine if they could develop into appropriate sinus cells, which they did. Despite the fact that these are preliminary findings, they are encouraging and show the promise and potential of cell-based treatment. 61-274

3.1 Highlights and Challenges

Many unique genetic techniques that get to the heart of the CF problem, overcoming a faulty gene, have been developed, and improvements in the nucleic acid therapy sector have made these methods much more practical as prospective therapies. However, there are a number of obstacles to overcome before any of these approaches can be used in clinical settings, including determining which organs should be targeted for the most robust effect with the least amount of potential harm; determining which cells should be targeted in each organ; and determining what constitutes a successful treatment.

Another consideration is that, unlike many other medicines, gene therapy and gene editing would need to move clinical trials forward without data from healthy adult control cohorts; instead, phase 1 investigations will require CF patients. Furthermore, for mutation-agnostic methods, we must decide which patients should be included in the initial studies: should we include all patients, even if effective modulator therapy is available, or should we only include those with no existing treatment options? Clearly, if we are to be successful, we must confront some serious obstacles, and we must do it as the collaborative group that we have always been.

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